

positive test of flavonoids with magnesium-hydrochloric acid. It was found to contain two methoxy groups as indicated by Zeisel experiment and exhibited $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 270 and 348 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400 br (bonded-OH), 1650, 1600 and 1580 cm^{-1} (chelated α,β -unsaturated C=O). These data in conjunction with the facts that the compound affords a monomethyl ether (2), $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ (M^+ 342) m.p. 105–08° on treatment with diazomethane and a dimethyl ether (3), $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ (M^+ 356), m.p. 95° on reaction with dimethyl sulphate suggest that the compound is dihydroxydimethoxyflavone. The ^1H nmr spectrum (90 MHz, CDCl_3) is also consistent with the above view and displayed signals due to one aromatic C-methyl at δ 2.05 (3H, s) and two aromatic methoxyls at δ 3.95 (6H, s). The A-ring proton at C₆-position appeared as a singlet at δ 6.55. The B-ring protons formed a ABX pattern, characteristic of 3',4'-dioxxygenated-flavonoids⁴. The 2'-proton showed up as a doublet at δ 7.85 (J 3 Hz) while 5'- and 6'-protons appeared as a doublet at δ 7.20 (J 8.5 Hz) and a quartet at δ 7.10 (J 3 and 8.5 Hz). The remaining proton resonance was a singlet at δ 6.35 assigned to the C₈-proton.

The monomethyl derivative (2) gave positive ferric chloride colour reaction indicating the presence of a chelated hydroxyl in the compound which must be at C₈-position. The position of the other hydroxyl group was settled from uv spectral measurement. As expected for flavonoids with free hydroxyl group at C₇-position, the short wavelength band at 270 nm shifted to 285 nm in presence of sodium acetate solution⁴ locating thereby the second hydroxyl group at C₇-position. All the above observations led to formulate the compound as 8-C-methyl-5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone (1) which appears to be new one. This structural assignment was confirmed by the isolation of veratric acid, m.p. 180–82°, and an acetophenone derivative, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 210), m.p. 143°, characterised as 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy-3-methylacetophenone⁵ from spectral studies [$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300 and 1685 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.10 (3H, ArCH_3), 2.50 (3H, COCH_3), 3.90 (6H, $2 \times \text{ArOCH}_3$), 6.97 (1H, ArH)] and comparison of physical constants from the alkaline degradation of the dimethyl derivative (3) with 40% KOH.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to R.S.I.C., Madras for spectral measurements, and to U.G.C., New

Delhi for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (C.K.C.).

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6-O-β-D-Glucosylscutellarein—A Rare Flavone Glycoside from *Stereospermum suaveolens*

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Manuscript received 9 November 1987, revised 11 December 1987, accepted 22 December 1987

*STEREOSPERMUM suaveolens*¹ D.C. (Fam. : Bignoniaceae) is a large deciduous tree found throughout the moist parts of India. The roots, bark and flowers are used in native medicine² and the root extract is known to have hypoglycemic and anticancer activities. This plant contains various higher carboxylic acids, β -sitosterol in the roots, lapachol and saponins in the entire plant³ and stereolensin (6-O-β-D-glucosylluteolin) in the leaves⁴.

During the course of pyrolysis chemical ionisation mass spectral analysis of flavonoid glycosides⁵, a sample of stereolensin was found to have another glycoside with molecular weight 16 amu lower as an impurity. The re-isolation of this minor component from *S. suaveolens* and its characterisation as 5,7,4'-trihydroxy-6-O-β-D-glucosylflavone (6-O-glucosylscutellarein), a rare natural product, are presented here.

Results and Discussion

A mixture of flavone glycosides obtained from the EtOAc-soluble fraction of the aqueous ethanolic concentrate of fresh leaves of *S. suaveolens* was resolved into two homogeneous compounds

(1 and 2) by two-stage preparative tlc (Polyamide DC₈; C₈H₈, MeOH, EtCOMe=4,3,3; R_f, 0.30 and 0.32 and microcrystalline cellulose; 60% HOAc; R_f, 0.55 and 0.70). Compound 1 was identified as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-6-O-β-D-glucosylflavone (6-glucosylxyluteolin, stereolensin) by uv, ¹H nmr, FABMS, hydrolysis with acid as well as the enzyme β-glucosidase in agreement with the earlier report⁴ and confirmed by co-R_f with an authentic sample.

Compound 2 could not be crystallised. Its solution in MeOH had R_f characteristic of a flavone glycoside^{6,7}. It underwent hydrolysis (0.5 M HCl, 30 min) to yield scutellarein and D-glucose. Identity of both the products were established beyond doubt by spectral analysis and glc comparison of the silylated derivatives with authentic compounds.

The glucoside exhibited uv absorption (intensity relative to most intense peak as 1.00) at (MeOH) 247sh, 271 (0.69), 292sh, 334 (1.00); (NaOMe) 257sh, 274 (0.58), 326 (0.38), 394 (1.00); (AlCl₃) 254sh, 280 (0.62), 288sh, 302 (0.65), 358 (1.00), 385sh; (AlCl₃-HCl) 253sh, 278 (0.67), 300 (0.71), 351 (1.00), 386sh; (NaOAc) 249sh, 273 (1.00), 289 (0.60), 300sh, 361 (0.80); (NaOAc-H₃BO₃) 249sh, 272 (1.00), 292 (0.70), 298 (0.63), 347 (0.82). Its ¹H nmr spectra (350 MHz, DMSO-d₆ and DMSO-d₆+1 drop of TFA, internal standard TMS) exhibited signals at δ 7.90 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 6.91 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 6.70 (1H, s, H-8), 6.41 (1H, s, H-3), 5.08 (1H, s, H-1 of glucose: appearing at 4.90 as 1H, d, J 8.5 Hz) with TFA), 4.95 and 4.67 (3H and 2H, m each, other glucose protons).

The uv spectra of 2 in MeOH and in presence of diagnostic reagents were very similar to 6-O-methylscutellarein⁸ and different from 7-O-methylscutellarein⁹. The AlCl₃ and AlCl₃/HCl spectra, besides indicating⁹ a blocked 6-OH, exhibited a shoulder around 385 nm which appears to be characteristic of 6-O-glycosylation on the basis of a similar observation earlier⁸. ¹H nmr spectra (resolution improved by adding one drop of TFA to DMSO-d₆ solution) showed signals characteristic of scutellarein and D-glucose moieties. The coupling constant (8.2 Hz) of H-1 of glucose revealed the β-configuration of the sugar. The negative ion FABMS of the glucoside exhibited peaks at 447 (M-H)⁻ and 285 (aglycone-H)⁻. Pyrolysis positive chemical ionisation (NH₃)MS with characteristic peaks at m/z 287 (aglycone+H)⁺ (100%), 180 (isobaric ion of glucose, replacing anomeric OH by NH₃) (100%), 162 (180-H₂O, 15%) and 145 (162-NH₃, 14%) and negative chemical ionisation (Cl⁻)MS with supporting complimentary peaks⁶ at m/z 285 (aglycone-H)⁻, 215 (glucose+Cl)⁻ (8%), 197 (215-H₂O, 100%), 179 (197-H₂O, 16%), 143 (glucose-H-2H₂O) (22%) further confirmed the nature of the aglycone as well as sugar. Based on the above data, 2 was characterised as 6-O-β-D-glucosyl scutellarein. The ring size of the sugar could not be established owing to paucity of material for ¹³C nmr analysis¹⁰. To our knowledge, this is the second record of occur-

ence of 6-O-glycosylscutellarein; the first being in *Haplopappus rengifoanus*¹¹ (Asteraceae). Contrary to earlier observations^{1,6,8} both the compounds, 6-O-glucosylxyluteolin and 6-O-glucosylapigenin were hydrolysed by β-glucosidase indicating that 6-O-glycosylation cannot be implicated in non-hydrolysability of these compounds. Successful β-glucosidase hydrolysis was also reported on the compound from *H. rengifoanus*. The ¹H nmr, negative FABMS as well as positive and negative CIMS data on this compound are reported for the first time. The earlier workers reported the ¹H nmr data on trimethyl silyl derivative.

Acknowledgement

The authors' grateful thanks are due to Dr. K. P. Madhusudan, Medicinal Chemistry Division, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for the CIMS data and useful discussion, and to Mr. Waton, C.N.R.S., Solaise, France, for the 350 MHz ¹H nmr data.

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Quantitative Determination of Metronidazole in Drug Preparations by Indirect Acid-Base Titration Method

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Manuscript received 1 June 1987, revised 21 December 1987, accepted 30 December 1987

An indirect acid-base method was employed for the quantitative determination of metronidazole in pharmaceutical dosage forms and compared with the other methods. The samples assayed were found to contain not less than 97.80 ± 0.12% of the drug and the technique is rapid and selective.